

Research Article

Design of Servo Motor Control System Based on SINAMICS S120

Yang Chao 杨超^{1*}, Shuvo Ahammed^{2*}

¹Electrical and New Energy Faculty of China Three Gorges University, Hubei Provincial Engineering Research Center of Intelligent Energy Technology, China Three Gorges University, China

²College of Electrical Engineering and New Energy, Department of Automation, China Three Gorges University, China

Corresponding author: Yang Chao

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Abstract: Motion control technology is a combined integration system of automation technology and electric drive technology. It integrates the latest achievements of microelectronics technology, computer technology, detection technology, automation technology and servo control technology. This paper is based on the advanced motion control system equipment of Siemens, PLC is programmed by computer software, and the servo motor is further controlled by the servo drive controller. The hardware and software of the system are configured by the software of Siemens, and the touch screen is added to the system. Finally, the servo motor is controlled by the touch screen. The Siemens S120 motion control system realizes the basic positioning function based on the previous system configuration, programming in the software, controlling the speed of servo motor, the speed and position of relative motion, the speed and position of absolute motion and the speed and speed ratio of synchronous motion, realizing the basic positioning function. PLC programming, the design of touch screen interface, through the direct control of touch screen makes the operation of the system more human-oriented, used PLC control servo motor drive controller, servo motor relative motion, absolute motion and synchronous motion control.

Keywords: Basic positioning, constant speed, synchronous and asynchronous motion, speed limit tracking, HMI touch screen control.

Introduction

Generally motion control means the use of servo and/or stepper systems as the “muscle” to move a given load. These motion control systems are capable of extremely precise speed, position, and torque control. Applications which require positioning of product, synchronization of separate elements, or rapid start/stop motion are all perfect candidates for the use of motion control. PLC

is very capable of providing the signals required to command these servo and stepper systems in a cost-effective and digital (noise-free) manner. In the information age, high and new technology flows to traditional industries, which causes profound changes in the latter. As one of the traditional industries, the mechanical industry, under the impact of this new technological revolution, has undergone a qualitative leap in product structure and production system structure. Micro electronic technology and micro computer technology combine information and intelligence with mechanical devices and power equipment, and promote the mechanical industry to start a large-scale mechanical and electrical integration technological revolution. With the development of computer electronic power and sensor technology, mechanical and electrical integration products emerge in an endless stream in various advanced countries. Machine tools, automobiles, instruments, household appliances, light industrial machinery, textile machinery, packaging machinery, printing machinery, metallurgical machinery, chemical machinery, industrial robots, intelligent robots and many other categories of products have made new progress every year. Mechatronics technology has been paid more and more attention in various aspects. It plays a great role in improving people's life, improving work efficiency, saving energy, reducing material consumption, enhancing enterprise competitiveness and so on. With the rapid development of mechatronics technology, motion control technology, as a key component of mechatronics technology, has been greatly developed. The multi-functional motion control training platform is a typical example of the application of motion control technology. It is derived from the abstract extraction of the typical production and processing process in the industrial field. It can provide disc synchronization, linear synchronization, disc type flying shear, material winding and other controlled object composition, so as to meet the teaching and training needs of different types and difficulties. The basic positioning function of the servo motor is realized by using the experimental equipment of Siemens advanced motion control system. The speed and position of the servo motor can be controlled by the touch screen, and the motion state of the servo motor can be monitored in real time to realize the automatic operation of the system. Drive Control Chart or DCC provides an extensible modular technology option, which is mainly used for driving related, continuous open-loop and closed-loop control engineering tasks. This DCC technology option for SINAMICS drives can be configured graphically using the CFC based drive control chart editor. This SINAMICS S120 is a new drive and control system which integrates V / F, vector control and servo control. It can not only control ordinary three-phase

asynchronous motor, but also control synchronous motor, torque motor and linear motor. Its powerful positioning function will realize the absolute and relative positioning of the feed axis. The internal integrated DCC function uses CFC programming language to realize logic, operation and simple process functions in PLC.

Design Requirements

DCC programming is used to debug the positioning, tracking and other functions of double disk (double axis motor); WinCC or HMI interface is used in the main computer to control the acceleration, constant speed, deceleration, positioning, tracking and synchronization of double disk (double axis motor). It is required to use SIMATIC S7 and TIA portal software to complete the hardware main circuit and PLC I/O interface circuit design, PLC program design, monitoring interface design, physical online debugging.

Main functions of design would be controlling the acceleration, constant speed, deceleration, positioning, tracking, synchronization, etc. of double disk (double axis motor).

Introduction of experimental equipment

The multifunctional motion control training platform is a typical example of the application of motion control technology. It is derived from the abstract extraction of the typical production and processing process in the industrial field. It can provide disc synchronization, linear synchronization, disc type flying shear, material winding and other controlled object composition, so as to meet the teaching and training needs of different types and difficulties. This multifunctional motion control platform used in this experiment is mainly composed of mainframe, control system electric cabinet, human-computer interaction panel and controlled object group. The schematic diagram is as follows:

Figure 1 Main components of multifunctional motion control training platform.

The dimensions of the main frame are: 1220mm long x 820mm wide x 820mm high, and the weight is about 80kg.

The electrical cabinet of this equipment is mainly installed with Siemens SIMATIC s7-t process control system, Siemens SINAMICS S120 high-performance drive system and low-voltage control and distribution products. The main components of SIMATIC s7-t process control system and SINAMICS S120 high performance drive system can refer to the following table:

The serial number	Product name and specification	Product order number	Number
1	POWER PS307	6ES7307-1EA01-0AA0	1
2	CPU 315T-3 PN/DP	6ES7315-7TJ10-0AB0	1
3	Memory Card MMC	6ES7953-8LP31-0AA0	1
4	DI Module SM323	6ES7323-1BL00-0AA0	1
5	AI Module SM334	6ES7331-0CE01-0AA0	1
6	Interface Module IM174	6ES7174-0AA10-0AA0	1

Table 1-1

SIMATIC s7-t process control system main components

The serial number	Product name and specification	Product order number	Number
1	Control Unit CU320-2 PN		1
2	Memory Card CF		1
3	Rectifier Unit SLM		1
4	Biaxial Motor DMM		1
5	Single Spindle Motor SMM		1
6	SERVO Motor		1

Table 1-2 Main components of SINAMICS S120 high-performance driver system

Human-computer interaction panel

Man-machine interaction panel is equipped with a Siemens KTP 700 BASIC PN (product order number: 6av2123-2gb03-0ax0) operating screen, which can be connected with CPU 315t-3

PN/DP or control unit cu320-2 PN through Ethernet cable. There are 20 double-position switches on the right side of the operation screen, among which 16 switches are connected to the control single cu320-2 PN, and 4 switches are connected to the terminal bank of the voltage distribution system.

Considering the connection according to the Seimens lab Before normal use of the system, various external wires shall be reliably connected. Refer to the diagram below for system connection

Figure 2-4 System wiring diagram-1

Figure 2-5 System wiring diagram-2

Power Rectifying

When the system is powered off, the incoming circuit of the rectifier module will be automatically disconnected. When the system is powered on again, the circuit will not be automatically connected. At the same time, for the consideration of safety protection, the multi-functional motion control training platform is also specially equipped with a group of safety gratings to ensure the operation safety. When an object enters the scanning range of the safety grating, the safety grating will send a signal to the driving system. When the driving system collects the signal sent by the safety grating, it will automatically cut off the incoming circuit of the rectifier module in the system, so that the motor cannot start or stop immediately, so as to prevent personal or mechanical injury. Therefore, when the system is powered on or the safety grating protection mechanism is triggered, the rectifier module needs to be powered on separately.

When the system has been powered up, but the incoming circuit of the rectifier module is not connected, the "RDY" indicator on the rectifier module will be displayed in orange, and the "DC link" indicator will be displayed in red.

Figure 2-6 :Rectifier unit not working

At this time, it is necessary to manually press the button as shown in the figure below to connect the incoming circuit of the rectifier module. When the incoming circuit of the rectifier module is connected, the "RDY" indicator on the rectifier module will be displayed in green, and the "DC link" indicator will be displayed in red. Check the working state of the rectifier module every time the system is powered on or the motor fails to rotate, so as to ensure that the rectifier module is in normal working state before the motor starts.

Switch use :

Figure 2-9: Toggle-inching switches

The human-computer interaction panel is equipped with 20 double position switches, 16 of which are connected to the control single cu320-2pn, and 4 are connected to the terminal strip of

the low-voltage distribution system. The usage of the two position switch is shown in the figure 2-9.

The controlled object of this experiment is a synchronous disk. The schematic diagram is as follows:

Figure 2-11: schematic diagram of disc synchronization object

The two discs of the disc synchronous object are all driven by the servo motor with reducer through the synchronous belt. The position shown in the figure is the initial position of the disc synchronization object.

Overview of SINAMICS S120

SINAMICS S120 is a new drive and control system which integrates V / F, vector control and servo control. It can not only control ordinary three-phase asynchronous motor, but also control synchronous motor, torque motor and linear motor. Its powerful positioning function will realize the absolute and relative positioning of the feed axis. The internal integrated DCC function uses PLC CFC programming language to realize logic, operation and simple process functions. The lower computer of this project adopts SINAMICS S120 frequency converter and SIMATIC s7-315t PLC, which enables students to master the practical application of S120 frequency

converter, debug the positioning and tracking functions of double disk (double axis motor) through DCC programming; the upper computer applies configuration software HMI interface, which can accelerate, constant speed, decelerate, locate, track and synchronize the double disk line control.

SINAMICS S120, as a new system architecture with central control unit, can drive and control all connected shafts, and can also establish technological interconnection between drivers. And it can be easily configured by clicking the mouse in the starter debugging tool:

- ✧ SINAMICS S120 control unit can independently solve simple process tasks
- ✧ cu310 series control unit is applicable to single axle drive
- ✧ cu320-2 control unit for multi-axle drive.

S120 drive system explain where the main control units under S120 drive

(1) CU310-2 DP and CU310-2 PN control unit : CU310-2 control unit is mainly used to control single drive. They are equipped with PROFIBUS interface (CU310-2 DP) or PROFINET interface (CU310-2 PN) and TTL / HTL encoder detection circuit as standard.

(2) CU320-2 control unit: CU320-2 control unit is mainly used to control multiple drives. CU320-2 control unit can control up to 12 drives (V / F control mode) and 6 drives (servo or vector control type).

Power module

The simplest version of a SINAMICS S120 drive system comprises a CU310-2 Control Unit and a Power Module. In Power Modules specifically designed for single-motor drives without regenerative feedback into the line supply, the line-side infeed and the motor-side power unit are combined in one unit

Generated energy produced during braking is converted to heat in braking resistors. The Control Unit is plugged onto the Power Module; In addition to the complete control intelligence, the Control Unit also has all the drive interfaces for communication with higher-level systems and interfacing of add-on components.

Line Modules contain the central line infeed for the DC link. Various Line Modules can be selected to address the various application profiles:

1. Basic Line Modules
2. Smart Line Modules
3. Active Line Modules

Motor module

A voltage source DC bus and a motor powered inverter are integrated in the motor module. CU320-2 control unit, power module and motor module diagram.

Motor Modules are designed for multi-axis drive systems and are controlled by either a CU320-2 or a SIMOTION D Control Unit. Motor Modules are interconnected through the DC link.

One or several Motor Modules are supplied with energy for the motors via the DC link. Both synchronous and induction motors can be operated. Since the Motor Modules share the same DC link, they can exchange energy with one another, i.e. if one Motor Module operating in generator mode produces energy, the energy can be used by another Motor Module operating in motor mode. The DC link is supplied with line supply voltage by a Line Module.

Starter

The common frequency converter can set the main parameters through the debugging panel, but because the S120 driver has powerful functions and many parameters, the special debugging software starter is generally used for debugging. There are two ways of hardware: missing through the RS-232 serial port debugging on S120, and installing adapter CP5512 on PC to connect through DP port. Starter mainly realizes the following functions:

- a) Hardware configuration and identification
- b) Parameter setting
- c) Debugging of dynamic characteristics
- d) Fault diagnosis
- e) Download and upload of program

Through the software starter, the status of the driver can be monitored online, and the motor can be run through the software control panel. In addition to control and monitoring, starter software can also mark the direction of speed channel in a graphical way. From speed setting to motor output, users can modify and monitor the control circuit parameters in a graphical way. Such a graphical design is more convenient for users to debug. For servo control, SINAMICS 120 also provides some debugging functions for users with the help of software starter, such as function generator, digital filter, data trace, Bode chart measurement function and automatic optimization function.

Hardware Configuration

Establishment of starter project

- 1) Create new project

2) Set "setpg / pcinterface" to the corresponding communication mode in option option

3) Read the connected equipment online through "accessiblenodes" and directly click the accept button below to complete the automatic reading of the drive unit settings.

4) Automatic configuration

Converter Parameter Configuration

1) Click Configure DDS (offline mode)

2) Change "0" to "1" and complete the configuration in turn

3) set encoder value

4) Click Finish to complete the converter parameter setting

Turn the Motor with the Control Panel

Click the control panel of the commissioning option under servo_02, click "give up control priority" in the yellow area, and give up the control priority. Set the motor speed, click green area 1, the motor can rotate, so that the normal motor can be judged quickly.

HMI

HMI is the interface between human (operator) and process (machine / equipment). PLC is the actual unit of control process. Therefore, there is an interface between the operator and WinCC flexible (located on the HMI device side) and between WinCC flexible and PLC. HMI system undertakes the following tasks:

- 1) Process visualization : The process is displayed on the HMI device. The screen on the HMI device can be updated dynamically according to the process change. This is based on changes in the process.
- 2) Operator's control of the process : The operator can control the process through the GUI (graphical user interface). For example, the operator can preset the reference value of the control or start the motor .
- 3) Display alarm : The critical state of the process automatically triggers an alarm, for example, when a set value is exceeded.
- 4) Archive process values and alarms : HMI system can record alarm and process value. This feature enables you to record sequence of process values and retrieve previous production data.
- 5) Process value and alarm record : HMI system can output alarm and process value report. For example, you can print out production data at the end of a shift.

Click "connect" in the left list, double-click "add", select the dancing program as "SIMATIC S7 300 / 400", change the IP address of HMI device and PLC to be consistent with the IP address searched by the node in starter software.

Experimental Process and Results

I / O port distribution:

Serial	Signal name	Signal source	Connection position
1	Switch input DI0	HMI switch DI0	+CU-X122:1
2	Switch input DI1	HMI switch DI1	+CU-X122:2
3	Switch input DI2	HMI switch DI2	+CU-X122:3
4	Switch input DI3	HMI switch DI3	+CU-X122:4
5	Switch input DI4	HMI switch DI4	+CU-X132:1
6	Switch input DI5	HMI switch DI5	+CU-X132:2
7	Switch input DI6	HMI switch DI6	+CU-X132:3

8	Switch input DI7	HMI switch DI7	+CU-X132:4
9	Switch input DI12	HMI switch DI12	+CU-X132:9
10	Switch input DI13	HMI switch DI13	+CU-X132:10
11	Switch input DI14	HMI switch DI14	+CU-X132:12
12	Switch input DI15	HMI switch DI15	+CU-X132:13
13	Switch input DI16	HMI switch DI16	+CU-X122:5
14	Switch input DI17	HMI switch DI17	+CU-X122:6
15	Switch input DI20	HMI switch DI20	+CU-X132:5
16	Switch input DI21	HMI switch DI21	+CU-X132:6

test procedure: SERVO_02 JOG and SERVO_04 JOG

DCC

Realization of touch screen and human-machine interface DCC programming procedure

Seven or modules respectively represent enable, big disk rotation, small disk rotation, zero return, big disk rotation 3 °, small disk rotation 3 °, big disk rotation to small disk 2 scale. The left side of the module is connected to the touch screen button.

Address	Module	Description	Value	OS	Operation	Count
1329	14841W0005	hardware sampling times available, hardware 1				
1340	14841W0005		0H		Operation	1
1341	14841W0005		0H		Operation	1
1342	14841W0005		0H		Operation	1
1343	14841W0005		0H		Operation	1
1344	14841W0005		0H		Operation	1
1345	14841W0005		0H		Operation	1
1346	14841W0005		0H		Operation	1
1347	14841W0005		0H		Operation	1
1348	14841W0005		0H		Operation	1
1349	14841W0005		0H		Operation	1
1350	14841W0005		0H		Operation	1
1351	14841W0005		0H		Operation	1
1352	14841W0005		0H		Operation	1
1353	14841W0005		0H		Operation	1

Parameters corresponding to OR module input in expert list.

Realization of human-computer interface(HMI)

1) Add button in root screen

2) set the variable in the variable table, select word as the data type, the operand identifier in the address is dB, and the DB number is the parameter in the starter corresponding to the button.

Address = 1024 * corresponding value of motor

The corresponding values of motors and driving units can be seen in the telegram configuration of starter

Object	Drive object	-No.	Telegram type	Input data	Output data
				Length	Length
1	SERVO_02	2	Free telegram configuration with BICO	0	0
2	SERVO_03	3	Free telegram configuration with BICO	0	0
3	SERVO_04	4	Free telegram configuration with BICO	0	0
4	Control_Unit	1	Free telegram configuration with BICO	0	0

Without PZDs (no cyclic data exchange)

Corresponding to touch screen buttons and implementation functions, variable table is

3) set the event function in the button event, set all button actions to click, set the event function to negate the bit in the variable, and select the variable corresponding to the button function in the variable (input / output) column.

4) compile and download, pg / PC interface type selection is the same as the device type, click "start search", wait a moment, search to HMI touch screen device, at this time, HMI device icon area turns yellow, click "download", then the program and screen edited in the blog can be downloaded to SIMATIC HMI device.

After downloading, the screen on the touch screen is as shown below. Click the button to control the size of the disc.

Conclusion

In this design, Siemens PLC, servo drive controller and touch screen are used to control the servo motor. The focus of the project is the PLC programming of the positioning system, the design of touch screen interface. Through the direct control of touch screen, the operation of the system is more humanized. PLC is used to control the servo motor drive controller, and the servo motor moves relative and absolute As the core of this project, the system is stable and the control effect is good. The basic positioning function of the servo motor is realized by using the experimental equipment of Siemens advanced motion control system. The speed and position of the servo motor can be controlled by the touch screen, and the motion state of the servo motor can be monitored in real time to realize the automatic operation of the system. Through this comprehensive operation, we not only have a deep understanding of the theoretical knowledge of motion control, but also greatly improve our practical ability, software simulation ability and professional drawing ability. Course assignment is the practical training of the comprehensive application of our professional course knowledge, which gives us the opportunity to apply the theoretical knowledge learned in the classroom to practice. And through the comprehensive use of knowledge, necessary practice and design. Thus further verify the theoretical knowledge we have learned, which is a necessary process before we step into the society and engage in professional work.

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Author Information

Name: 杨超 (Yangchao)

E-mail: copy_yangchao@163.com

Mobile: +8615997601292

Place: Electrical and New Energy Faculty of China Three Gorges University, Hubei Provincial Engineering Research Center of Intelligent Energy Technology, China Three Gorges University, China.

Name: SHUVO AHAMMED

E-mail: mdshuvo_ahmed@yahoo.com

Mobile: +8613177088908

Bachelor of Automation, College of Electrical Engineering and New Energy, China Three Gorges University, China.

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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The graphic features a stylized green globe with a plant growing from it, set against a background of radiating lines.

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